

FREQUENCY OF CAROTID ARTERY DISEASE AND ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the frequency of carotid artery disease and its associated risk factors in patients with ischemic stroke at a tertiary care hospital.

Design: Cross-sectional study

Place and duration of the study: Department of Medicine, Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi from 26-May-2023 to 25-Nov-2023.

Methods: The study included 150 patients of both genders, their age varies between 18 - 90 years, admitted with confirmed ischemic stroke. Patients with hemorrhagic stroke, space-occupying lesions, brain infections, or septic emboli were excluded. Data on demographics, comorbidities, and carotid Doppler ultrasound to assess the presence and degree of carotid artery disease were collected on structured proforma. The degree of stenosis was categorized as mild (<50%), moderate (50–69%), or severe (≥70%). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 24. Chi-square test used to identify risk factors. A *p*-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results: The mean age was 65.8 ± 13.9 years, and 64.7% were male. Hypertension 78.0%, diabetes 44.7%, and hyperlipidemia 36.7% were common comorbidities. Carotid artery disease was present in 53.3% of the participants, Carotid stenosis was present in 32% of the participants, while 10.0% had severe stenosis. In terms of ethnicity, Mohajirs were the largest group, representing 34.7% of the participants, followed by Sindhis at 23.3%, and Punjabis at 18.0%. Significant associations with carotid artery disease were observed for older age (*p* = 0.040), higher BMI (*p* = 0.005), and smoking history (*p* < 0.001).

Conclusion: A notable proportion of ischemic stroke patients had underlying carotid artery disease, particularly those who were older, obese, or smokers. The findings of this study emphasize on routine carotid screening in high-risk populations to inform targeted preventive strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a health challenge, it is the second major cause of mortality and third leading cause of physical and mental impairment worldwide. Among all stroke types, ischemic stroke comprises of 85% of cases.(1)

One of the most preventable and treatable causes of ischemic stroke is carotid artery disease, which results from atherosclerotic narrowing or occlusion of the extracranial carotid arteries, particularly the internal

carotid artery.(2) Carotid artery disease contributes to stroke by reducing cerebral perfusion or by serving as a source of emboli that travel to the brain. the early identification and management of carotid artery disease in stroke patients are therefore essential components of effective stroke prevention and treatment strategies.(3)

Despite the clinical importance of carotid artery disease, there is a significant knowledge gap regarding its frequency and risk factor profile among ischemic stroke patients in developing countries, particularly in South Asia.(4) In Pakistan, the burden of stroke is rising at an alarming rate due to rapid urbanization, demographic transition, and an increase in modifiable risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, tobacco use, dyslipidemia, obesity, and physical inactivity.(5) The lack of organized stroke surveillance systems and limited diagnostic capacity further exacerbate the challenge of accurately estimating disease burden and implementing timely interventions.(6)

Current estimates suggest that the prevalence of stroke in Pakistan ranges from 4.8% to 19.1% in different population groups, with a disproportionate impact on younger adults compared to high-income countries.(7, 8) However, data specific to the prevalence of carotid artery disease among ischemic stroke patients in Pakistan remain scarce and fragmented. This gap in knowledge undermines the ability of clinicians and health policy makers to identify high risk individuals and allocate resources effectively for stroke prevention. Moreover, while guidelines in high-income settings advocate for routine carotid imaging in selected stroke patients, the utility, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness of such strategies in resource-constrained Pakistani hospitals have not been adequately explored.(8)

Tertiary care hospitals in Pakistan function as major referral centers and manage a large volume of acute stroke cases from both urban and rural catchment areas. These settings provide a unique opportunity to investigate the burden and clinical profile of carotid artery disease in ischemic stroke patients and to identify locally relevant risk factors.(5) Understanding the interplay of these factors is crucial in tailoring evidence based interventions, such as carotid revascularization procedures (e.g., carotid endarterectomy or stenting), medical management,

and lifestyle modifications, within the framework of the Pakistani healthcare system.(9, 10)

In this context, the current study is designed to determine the frequency of carotid artery disease and its associated risk factors among patients admitted with ischemic stroke at a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. By generating a context- specific evidence, the study focus to fill a crucial loophole in the national stroke research agenda and support the development of targeted screening protocols, risk stratification tools, and resource-appropriate clinical pathways to bring down the stroke-related physical impairment and deaths.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine at the Aga Khan University Hospital (AKUH), Karachi. The study period spanned six months, from May 26, 2023, to November 25, 2023. Methodological rigor was ensured by adhering to the STROBE guidelines for cross-sectional studies, which provide a standardized framework for transparent and comprehensive reporting of observational research.

The study population comprised adult patients of both sexes aged between 18 and 90 years, admitted with a radiologically confirmed diagnosis of ischemic stroke. Ischemic stroke was diagnosed based on neuroimaging findings, specifically hypodense areas observed on computed tomography scans or hyperintense lesions on magnetic resonance imaging consistent with acute cerebral infarction. This inclusion criterion ensured the diagnostic accuracy and clinical relevance of the study findings. Patients were excluded if they presented with hemorrhagic stroke, space-occupying intracranial lesions, central nervous system infections (e.g., meningitis, encephalitis, or brain abscess), or septic emboli, to avoid confounding conditions that could mimic ischemic stroke or independently affect carotid artery morphology.

Data were collected prospectively using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to obtain detailed sociodemographic information (age, gender, ethnicity), as well as key clinical variables including the presence of known vascular risk factors: diabetes mellitus, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, smoking history, and ischemic heart disease. These

variables were selected based on their well-established associations with both carotid artery disease and ischemic stroke in international literature, and their high prevalence within the Pakistani population.

To assess the presence and severity of carotid artery disease, doppler ultrasonography of the carotid arteries was conducted by trained radiologists using standardized imaging protocols based on internationally recognized criteria. The severity of stenosis was classified into three categories: mild (<50%), moderate (50–69%), and severe (≥70%), also noting the presence of atherosclerotic plaques.

150 patients were enrolled in the study through a non-probability consecutive sampling technique, which allowed for the inclusion of all eligible patients during the study time frame, thereby minimizing selection bias. The sample size was calculated based on an estimated carotid artery disease prevalence of 53.7% (derived from relevant literature), with a 95% confidence level and 8% margin of error, ensuring adequate statistical power to detect meaningful associations.

All data were entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were summarized as means with standard deviations (SD). Categorical variables were described using frequencies and percentages. To evaluate potential confounding and effect-modifying factors, stratified analyses were

conducted based on age groups, gender, and individual clinical risk factors. Chi-square tests were used to identify associations between categorical variables such as age groups, gender, ethnicity, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, chronic kidney disease and smoking between groups (carotid artery disease +ve and carotid artery disease -ve). A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant throughout the analysis.

Results

A total of 150 patients were enrolled in the study. The mean age of participants was 65.8 years (±13.9). Of the total, 26.7% were younger than 57 years. Males constituted the majority, comprising 64.7% of the participants, yielding a male-to-female ratio of 1.8:1. In terms of ethnicity, Mohajirs were the largest group, representing 34.7% of the participants, followed by Sindhis at 23.3%, and Punjabis at 18.0%. The mean body mass index (BMI) was 24.5 kg/m² (±3.2), with over half (53.3%) having a BMI within the normal range of 18.5 to 24.9. Hypertension was the most common risk factor identified, present in 78.0% of participants. This was followed by diabetes mellitus in 44.7% and hyperlipidemia in 36.7%. Carotid artery disease was observed in 53.3% of the patients. In terms of carotid stenosis, 68.0% of participants showed no signs of stenosis, while 10.0% had severe stenosis (Table I).

Table 1: Characteristics of study participants

Age	
– Mean ± SD	65.8±13.9
– <57 years	40 (26.7%)
– 57-66 years	36 (24.0%)
– 67-77 years	37 (24.7%)
– >77 years	37 (24.7%)
Gender	
– Male	97 (64.7%)
– Female	53 (35.3%)
Ethnicity	
– Sindhi	35 (23.3%)
– Punjabi	27 (18.0%)
– Pakhtoon	18 (12.0%)
– Balo chi	18 (12.0%)
– Mohajir	52 (34.7%)
Body mass index	

- Mean ± SD	24.5±3.2
- <18.5	3 (2.0%)
- 18.5 to 24.9	80 (53.3%)
- 25 to 29.9	54 (36.0%)
- ≥30	13 (8.7%)
Risk factors	
- Diabetes Mellitus	67 (44.7%)
- Hypertension	117 (78.0%)
- Hyperlipidemia	55 (36.7%)
- Ischemic heart disease	41 (27.3%)
- Chronic kidney disease	20 (13.3%)
- Smoking	54 (36.0%)
Frequency of Carotid artery disease	80 (53.3%)
Degree of Carotid artery stenosis	
- None	102 (68.0%)
- Mild (<50%)	23 (15.3%)
- Moderate (50-69%)	10 (6.7%)
- Severe (≥70%)	15 (10.0%)

The frequency of carotid artery disease rose steadily with age, 37.5% in participants younger than 57 years, 52.8% in those aged 57-66 years, 54.1% in the 67-77-year group, and 70.3% in individuals older than 77 years (p = 0.040). When comparing BMI categories,

carotid artery disease was significantly more frequent in obese participants (76.9%) compared to underweight participants (66.7%; p = 0.005). Smoking showed the strongest association: 75.9% of smokers had carotid artery disease, compared with 40.6% of non-smokers (p < 0.001) - Table II.

Table 2: Comparison of risk factors of study participants with and without carotid artery disease

	Carotid Artery Disease		P-value
	Yes (n=80)	No (n=70)	
Age			
<57 years	15 (37.5%)	25 (62.5%)	0.040
57-66 years	19 (52.8%)	17 (47.2%)	
67-77 years	20 (54.1%)	17 (45.9%)	
>77 years	26 (70.3%)	11 (29.7%)	
Gender			
Male	57 (58.8%)	40 (41.2%)	0.051
Female	23 (43.4%)	30 (56.6%)	
Body mass index			
<18.5	2 (66.7%)	1 (33.3%)	0.005
18.5 to 24.9	32 (40.0%)	48 (60.0%)	
25 to 29.9	36 (66.7%)	18 (33.3%)	
≥30	10 (76.9%)	3 (23.1%)	
Ethnicity			
Sindhi	20 (57.1%)	15 (42.9%)	0.755
Punjabi	14 (51.9%)	13 (48.1%)	

Pakhtoon	10 (55.6%)	8 (44.4%)	
Balochi	7 (38.9%)	11 (61.1%)	
Mohajir	29 (55.8%)	23 (44.2%)	
Comorbid conditions			
Diabetes mellitus	33 (49.3%)	34 (50.7%)	0.321
Hypertension	66 (56.4%)	51 (43.6%)	0.110
Hyperlipidemia	26 (47.3%)	29 (52.7%)	0.168
Ischemic Heart Disease	25 (61.0%)	16 (39.0%)	0.167
Chronic kidney disease	13 (65.0%)	7 (35.0%)	0.189
Smoking	41 (75.9%)	13 (24.1%)	<0.001

Discussion

This study investigated the prevalence and risk factors associated with carotid artery disease among ischemic stroke patients presenting at a tertiary care center in Karachi, Pakistan. Findings revealed that 53.3% of the participants had carotid artery disease, out of which 32% of the patients exhibited carotid artery stenosis, with 10% presenting with severe stenosis ($\geq 70\%$ luminal narrowing). The most frequently reported risk factors included hypertension (78.0%), diabetes mellitus (44.7%), hyperlipidemia (36.7%), and ischemic heart disease (27.3%). Statistically significant associations with carotid stenosis were identified for age ($p = 0.040$), body mass index (BMI) ($p = 0.005$), and smoking status ($p < 0.001$).

Age came out as a noteworthy risk factor for carotid artery disease, with elderly person demonstrating a ubiquity of carotid narrowing. This finding is compatible with prior evidence that atherosclerosis progresses with advancing age (11, 12). Elevated BMI was strongly associated with increased stenosis, reflecting the inflammatory and metabolic contributions of obesity to atherosclerotic plaque development.(13, 14) Smoking was identified as the most impactful modifiable risk factor, with significantly higher carotid artery disease prevalence observed among tobacco users. (15, 16) This is attributable to the role of smoking in accelerating atherosclerosis through mechanisms such as endothelial injury, enhanced blood coagulability, and chronic inflammation.(17)

Although hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and hyperlipidemia were among the most frequently observed risk factors in this study, these factors did not show statistically significant associations with carotid artery disease. This unexpected finding may be

attributed to multiple potential reasons. Biologically, it is possible that the chronic nature and high prevalence of these conditions in the study population reduced their discriminative power in identifying individuals at higher risk for carotid artery disease.

The findings align with regional data, including studies from southern India and the Punjab Institute of Cardiology, which reported carotid stenosis prevalence rates of approximately 30% and 35.2%, respectively.(18, 19) In Pakistan, stroke remains a leading cause of morbidity, compounded by limited public awareness and restricted access to diagnostic services. This study underscores the importance of routine carotid screening in high-risk populations.(20) A noteworthy strength of this study is the utilization of carotid Doppler ultrasonography, a non-invasive and widely validated imaging modality. All scans were performed by trained radiologists, ensuring diagnostic consistency and reliability. The study further benefitted from standardized definitions of risk factors and structured data collection protocols, minimizing potential information bias. The findings offer practical utility for clinicians operating in tertiary care settings, providing evidence to guide risk stratification and stroke prevention strategies.

However, few constraints should be acknowledged. Methodologically, the cross-sectional study design limits the ability to institute temporal relationships between risk factors and carotid stenosis, thus hindering causal inference. Additionally, relevant variables such as physical activity, dietary habits, medication adherence, and detailed family medical history were not captured. Including these factors could have strengthened the interpretation of findings by providing further insights into the multifactorial etiology of carotid artery disease. The implications of

these findings are significant for both clinical practice and health policy.

In conclusion, nearly one-third of ischemic stroke patients in this cohort exhibited carotid artery stenosis, with age, BMI, and smoking demonstrating significant associations. These findings underscore the importance of routine carotid screening and targeted risk-based management strategies, especially for older adults, individuals with elevated BMI, and smokers presenting with ischemic stroke. Adoption of targeted prevention strategies and investment in diagnostic infrastructure may contribute substantially to reducing stroke recurrence and improving outcomes, particularly in resource constrained settings. Ongoing research and policy engagement will be critical to translating these findings into effective public health interventions.

Conclusion:

A notable proportion of ischemic stroke patients had underlying carotid artery disease, particularly those who were older, obese or smokers. The findings of this study emphasize on routine carotid screening in high-risk populations to inform targeted preventive strategies.

Ethical approval

This study was approved by the ethical review committee of Aga Khan University (ERC number: 2023-7946-24215).

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Authors contribution

Dr. Summaya Fatima conceptualized the study, developed the methodology, Collected data, conducted data analysis and interpretation, and drafted the manuscript.

Dr. Hafiz Mehmood Riaz supervised Dr. Summaya Fatima to conceptualize and develop methodology. Data interpretation. Feedback on manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved this final manuscript for publication.

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